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Raising Up Leaders: A Holistic Mentoring Program for Youth Ministry

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop a holistic mentoring program designed for youth ministry leaders in the United Methodist Church (UMC), Philippines. Recognizing the challenges faced by young leaders in Christian ministry—including gaps in spiritual formation, personality development, communication skills, and leadership abilities—the research employed a quantitative-descriptive design to assess leadership needs across five key domains. A validated questionnaire was administered to 160 respondents, composed of current and former youth officers. Results indicated that spiritual formation emerged as the highest-ranked leadership need, followed closely by personality development and communication skills. The data also revealed a lack of structured mentoring systems within the district, with most leadership development occurring informally. In response, a five-module Holistic Mentoring Program was designed, integrating biblical principles, leadership theory, and practical ministry strategies. The program sought to cultivate Christlike character, nurture personal growth, and develop essential leadership competencies through intentional mentorship, guided reflection, and community engagement. By encouraging a culture of mentoring within youth ministry, this study provides a replicable model for faith communities seeking to empower the next generation of servant-leaders. The study highlighted the importance of intentional mentoring in shaping future leaders and encourages further research on its implementation across different denominational contexts.

Keywords: mentoring, youth ministry, leadership development, spiritual formation

Introduction

Youth ministry is vital in nurturing future Christian leaders, providing young people opportunities for discipleship, service, and leadership development (Aziz, 2022). However, sustaining effective youth leadership presents challenges, including limited mentorship, underdeveloped personal and spiritual growth, and inadequate preparation for ministry's complexities (Kim, 2020). Without structured guidance, youth ministry risks becoming a revolving door—leading to leadership voids and diminishing the vitality of church programs (Cruz & Leon, 2023). Effective leadership formation requires intentional mentorship, where experienced church leaders guide young people in discerning their calling and nurturing their gifts (Msebi & Beukes, 2024). Studies emphasize the need for structured training to address burnout among youth leaders, who often feel unsupported in their roles (Kim, 2020). Youth engagement and appreciation of their contributions are essential for encouraging a healthy, sustainable church community (Rumeli et al., 2021). The dynamics between youth and church leadership significantly impact leadership development, with research showing that participation in youth ministries promotes a sense of belonging and active contribution (Darmawan et al., 2024). Integrating biblical and practical experience equips young leaders for contemporary ministry challenges (Eden & Onyebuchi, 2024). Access to relevant training resources is also critical for preparing youth mentors and leaders (Cabaniss, 2023). These challenges are reflected in the context of the United Methodist Church in the Philippines where Church leaders report occasional issues: inconsistent leadership practices, declining youth engagement, and burnout among young officers.

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While the United Methodist Youth Fellowship (UMYF) offers a platform for leadership, the lack of a structured mentoring system often leads to gaps in spiritual formation, personal maturity, and ministry skills. This study aimed to develop a holistic mentoring program that addresses the identified leadership needs of youth leaders. Anchored in practical theology, the study applied Osmer's (2008) four tasks—description, interpretation, normative reflection, and pragmatic response—to explore how churches can nurture servant-leaders. By combining empirical research, theological reflection, and practical application, this study offers a contextualized mentoring framework aligned with biblical models, particularly Jesus' servant leadership (Philippians 2:5–8) and the Great Commission (Matthew 28:19–20). The program seeks to encourage Christlike character, personal transformation, and active community engagement, contributing to the broader conversation on youth leadership formation in the church (Maxwell, 2007).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative-descriptive research design to systematically assess the leadership needs of youth officers in the United Methodist Church Northeast Pangasinan District (UMC NEPD). The design was chosen for its suitability in providing an overview of leadership gaps and needs across the district (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The findings guided the development of a contextualized mentoring program, reflecting Osmer's (2008) model of practical theology, which emphasizes description, interpretation, normative reflection, and pragmatic response.

Participants and Sampling

The study utilized purposive sampling to select 20 local churches within the United Methodist Church, specifically in the Northeast Pangasinan District (NEPD). These churches were chosen based on their active participation in UMYF ministry, representing a range of rural and urban contexts within the district. While the study focuses on this specific district, the findings aim to provide insights applicable to broader denominational settings. Respondents were UMYF local and district officers from the 20 churches, following the UMYF Constitution's eight official leadership positions. A total of 160 respondents were surveyed, including current officers (priority 1), past officers within the UMYF age range of 12–23 (priority 2), and general UMYF members when officer positions were unfilled (priority 3). Demographic data revealed that the majority of respondents were female (55.62%) and within the 16–19 age range (46.25%). Most respondents had 0–2 years of leadership experience, indicating a youthful leadership base with limited tenure. These factors may influence the findings, as younger, less-experienced leaders may prioritize certain needs differently compared to more seasoned youth leaders.

Instrumentation

Data were gathered using a researcher-developed questionnaire designed to assess leadership needs across five domains: spiritual formation, personality development, communication skills, leadership abilities, and other essential skills. The instrument underwent content validation by three experts in Christian education and youth ministry, ensuring its relevance and clarity. A pilot test was conducted among a small group of youth leaders, resulting in minor revisions for improved clarity. The final questionnaire employed a 4-point Likert scale (1 = Not Needed, 2 = Little Needed, 3 = Needed, 4 = Highly Needed) to capture respondents' perceptions.

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Data Collection Procedures

Data collection was conducted with the cooperation of church leaders, who facilitated survey distribution during district assemblies and local church meetings. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose, voluntary nature, and confidentiality measures. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw at any stage without penalty.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, weighted means, and standard deviations, were utilized to analyze the data. This approach provided a clear profile of leadership needs, guiding the design of the mentoring program.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical research standards, ensuring participant anonymity, data confidentiality, and voluntary participation. Ethical approval was sought through consultation with the church leadership.

Limitations

This study's findings are limited by its specific context within UMC NEPD. While the study offers valuable insights into youth leadership needs, the results may not fully capture the experiences of other districts or denominations. Additionally, the sample's gender imbalance (majority female) and concentration of respondents within the 16–19 age group may affect the generalizability of results, as perspectives from older or more experienced leaders were underrepresented. The study focused on the development of a Holistic Mentoring Program rather than its implementation. As such, feasibility challenges—such as mentor availability, time constraints, and resource limitations—were not addressed in this research. Future studies could explore the practical barriers and long-term effectiveness of implementing the proposed program across diverse church contexts.

Results

The leadership needs assessment gathered responses from 160 participants across 20 local churches within the United Methodist Church Northeast Pangasinan District. The findings reveal a strong consensus among respondents regarding the leadership needs of youth in ministry, with relatively low standard deviations (0.40–0.55) indicating consistent perceptions (Boone & Boone, 2012; Norman, 2010).

As shown in **Table 1**, **Spiritual Formation** emerged as the highest priority ($M = 3.17$, $SD = 0.42$), highlighting the foundational role of nurturing a deep relationship with God in effective leadership (Philippians 2:5–8). Respondents identified *prayer life* and *church involvement* as the most critical aspects of spiritual formation. **Personality Development** ($M = 3.16$, $SD = 0.55$) followed closely, emphasizing the importance of *positive attitude* and *confidence*. **Communication Skills** ($M = 3.07$, $SD = 0.43$) also ranked highly, with *active listening* emerging as the most needed skill, underscoring the relational nature of ministry (Severe & Senter, 2020).

Leadership Abilities ($M = 3.04$) and **Other Essential Skills** ($M = 3.01$) were also identified as important domains, with respondents highlighting *building relationships*, *problem-solving*, *time management*, and *conflict resolution* as key competencies for effective ministry.

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These findings underscore the need for a **holistic mentoring program** that integrates spiritual formation, character development, communication, leadership abilities, and practical ministry skills to equip youth for sustainable leadership in the church.

Leadership Needs Assessment

Leadership Domain	Mean	SD	Rank
Spiritual Formation	3.17	0.42	1
Personality Development	3.16	0.55	2
Communication Skills	3.07	0.43	3
Leadership Abilities	3.04	0.40	4
Other Essential Skills	3.01	0.41	5

Table 1. Leadership Needs Assessment

Note. N = 160 respondents from 20 local churches within the UMC. Mean values represent the perceived importance of each leadership domain, rated on a 4-point Likert scale (1 = Not Needed, 2 = Little Needed, 3 = Needed, 4 = Highly Needed). Standard deviation (SD) indicates variability in responses; SD values between 0.40 and 0.55 reflect a moderate to strong consensus among respondents, indicating that most of them consistently agreed on the importance of these leadership domains.

Specific Leadership Needs

Table 2 presents the five highest-rated specific leadership needs which reflect a mix of spiritual formation and practical leadership capabilities, emphasizing the need for a mentoring program. Prayer life (M = 3.31, SD = 0.63) ranked as the most critical need, reflecting the foundational role of a deep and active relationship with God in shaping effective youth leaders. The relatively moderate standard deviation indicates some variability in respondents' perceptions, possibly influenced by differing levels of emphasis on personal spirituality across churches. Positive attitude (M = 3.26, SD = 0.79) and confidence (M = 3.25, SD = 0.69), both under the category of personality development, ranked second and third respectively. These findings highlight the importance of emotional intelligence, resilience, and self-assurance in ministry leadership. The higher standard deviations (especially for positive attitude) show that people have very different opinions. While many think these traits are important, people may disagree on how important they are or what they actually mean. Church involvement (M = 3.22, SD = 0.64) ranked fourth, underscoring the value of active participation in ministry as part of leadership development. Its moderate SD indicates a shared recognition of its importance, albeit with some variation in emphasis. Active listening (M = 3.18, SD = 0.68) was identified as the top communication skill need, emphasizing the relational aspect of ministry and the ability to engage and empathize with others. The SD suggests some variation in perceptions, perhaps reflecting differences in local church communication practices.

Leadership Need	Category	Mean	SD	Rank
Prayer Life	Spiritual Formation	3.31	0.63	1
Positive Attitude	Personality Development	3.26	0.79	2
Confidence	Personality Development	3.25	0.69	3
Church Involvement	Spiritual Formation	3.22	0.64	4
Active Listening	Communication Skills	3.18	0.68	5

Table 2. Specific Leadership Needs

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Discussion

This study highlights the critical need for a **holistic approach** to leadership development within the United Methodist Church. The leadership needs assessment revealed that while spiritual formation is highly prioritized ($M = 3.17$, $SD = 0.42$), effective leadership also requires growth in personality development, communication skills, and practical ministry competencies. The relatively low standard deviations ($0.42-0.79$) suggest moderate to strong consensus among respondents, affirming the shared recognition that leadership in youth ministry is both a spiritual and practical calling (Boone & Boone, 2012; Norman, 2010). The prominence of **prayer life** ($M = 3.31$) as the top leadership need reflects the biblical truth that ministry flows from a deep relationship with God (Philippians 2:5-8). As Greenleaf (2002) emphasizes, servant-leaders are rooted in a life of spiritual reflection and service. Similarly, the high rankings for **positive attitude** ($M = 3.26$) and **confidence** ($M = 3.25$) underscore the importance of emotional intelligence and resilience in leadership (Maxwell, 2015; Rumeli et al., 2021). The need for **active listening** ($M = 3.18$) aligns with the relational nature of ministry, where effective communication builds trust and community (Severe & Senter, 2020).

In response to the leadership needs identified in the study, a Holistic Mentoring Program is proposed as a structured framework for developing well-rounded, Christlike leaders in the United Methodist Church. The program is designed to address five core leadership domains: spiritual formation, personality development, communication skills, leadership abilities, and other essential skills.

The program is intended for a six-month mentoring cycle, with weekly sessions (1.5-2 hours each) facilitated by trained mentors. Each mentor is assigned 3-5 mentees to ensure personalized guidance while fostering peer accountability and learning. The program is adaptable for local churches, district youth groups, or conference-level initiatives. While the data were gathered from the Northeast Pangasinan District, the proposed program is designed for adaptability across various United Methodist Church contexts in the Philippines and beyond.

Each module includes:

Biblical Foundations (Scripture study and reflection)

- Theoretical Input (mini-lectures, readings, and discussion)
- Practical Activities (hands-on exercises, role-plays, and case studies)
- Reflection and Application (journaling, feedback, and ministry assignments)

Module Descriptions and Sample Activities

1. Spiritual Formation

Objective: Deepen personal faith and cultivate a life of prayer, devotion, and service.

Sample Activities:

Weekly devotional reflections on Philippians 2:5-8, John 15:5

Prayer partnerships and small group intercession

Guided journaling: "Where do I sense God's calling in my life?"

Leading a short devotion or prayer in a church gathering

Expected Outcomes: Mentees demonstrate consistent devotional habits, lead a small prayer group, and articulate their faith journey.

2. Personality Development

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Objective: Promote Christlike character, emotional intelligence, and self-awareness.

Sample Activities:

Role-plays: Responding to conflict with grace

Group reflection: The Fruit of the Spirit (Galatians 5:22–23) in leadership

Self-assessment: Strengths, weaknesses, and growth areas

Expected Outcomes: Mentees exhibit growth in confidence, resilience, and positive attitude.

3. Communication Skills

Objective: Enhance listening, speaking, and writing skills for ministry effectiveness.

Sample Activities:

Active listening drills: Reflective listening practice

Public speaking: Prepare and deliver a 5-minute message

Sermon writing workshop: Outlining a simple devotional message

Expected Outcomes: Mentees engage in meaningful conversations, deliver short talks, and write simple ministry reports.

4. Leadership Abilities

Objective: Build core leadership skills for ministry, including decision-making, teamwork, and problem-solving.

Sample Activities:

Ministry project planning: Design a small outreach event

Team simulations: Delegating tasks and solving challenges

Reflection: “What makes a leader trustworthy?” (2 Timothy 2:2)

Expected Outcomes: Mentees lead a small ministry initiative, work collaboratively, and reflect on leadership experiences.

5. Other Essential Skills

Objective: Equip mentees with practical skills for ministry sustainability.

Sample Activities:

Time management workshop: Balancing ministry, study, and family

Conflict resolution role-play: Navigating disagreements in the church

Review of church policies: Understanding basic governance

Expected Outcomes: Mentees apply time management strategies, handle conflicts constructively, and understand church structures.

Conclusion

This study affirmed that nurturing youth leaders within the United Methodist Church requires a holistic approach that integrates spiritual formation, character development, and practical leadership skills. The leadership needs assessment revealed a strong emphasis on foundational spiritual practices such as prayer life, personal devotion, and church involvement, alongside the development of positive attitudes, communication skills, and time management. These findings underscore the reality that leadership in the church is both a spiritual calling and a practical responsibility. The proposed Holistic Mentoring Program seeks to address these identified needs by offering a structured, contextualized, and biblically grounded framework for mentoring youth leaders. By focusing on five core domains—spiritual formation, personality development, communication skills, leadership abilities, and other essential skills—the program equips young leaders to serve with confidence, competence, and Christlike character. At its end goal, this study challenges churches to recognize mentoring not as an

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optional program but as an essential ministry practice that ensures the sustainability of leadership for future generations. Further research is recommended to assess the program's long-term impact and adaptability across diverse church settings. This mentoring model, though rooted in the Philippine context, provides a replicable framework for nurturing youth leaders in diverse denominational and cultural settings.

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